

Water Adsorption Enhances Electrical Conductivity in Transparent P-type CuI

Andrea Crovetto,^{*,†} Hannes Hempel,[†] Marin Rusu,[†] Leo Choubrac,[†] Danny Kojda,[‡] Klaus Habicht,^{‡,¶} and Thomas Unold[†]

[†]*Department of Structure and Dynamics of Energy Materials, Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin für Materialien und Energie, Hahn-Meitner Platz 1, 14109 Berlin, Germany*

[‡]*Department of Methods for Characterization of Transport Phenomena in Energy Materials, Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin für Materialien und Energie, Hahn-Meitner Platz 1, 14109 Berlin, Germany*

[¶]*Institute of Physics and Astronomy, University of Potsdam, Karl-Liebknecht-Str. 24-25, D-14476 Potsdam*

E-mail: andrea.crovetto@helmholtz-berlin.de

Abstract

CuI has been recently rediscovered as a p-type transparent conductor with a high figure of merit. Even though many metal iodides are hygroscopic, the effect of moisture on the electrical properties of CuI has not been clarified. In this work, we observe a two-fold increase in the conductivity of CuI after exposure to ambient humidity for 5 hours, followed by slight long-term degradation. Simultaneously, the work function of CuI decreases by almost 1 eV, which can explain the large spread in the previously reported work function values. The conductivity increase is partially reversible and is maximized at intermediate humidity levels. Based on the large intra-grain mobility measured by THz spectroscopy, we suggest that hydration of grain boundaries may be beneficial for the overall hole mobility.

Keywords

transparent conductors, CuI, copper iodide, conductivity, humidity, p-type, work function

Introduction

Electron-doped transparent conductive materials (n-type TCMs) are used routinely as optically transparent electrical contacts in solar cells and displays.¹⁻⁴ The performance of a given thin-film material as a TCM can be quantified using one of the several figures of merit (FOM) proposed by various authors.¹⁻³ A widely adopted FOM is simply the ratio between the electrical conductivity and the absorption coefficient of the material averaged over the visible region.³ A few different n-type oxides have FOMs between $1 \Omega^{-1}$ and $10 \Omega^{-1}$, which are sufficiently high to satisfy the requirements of many optoelectronic devices.³ Conversely, the development of hole-doped (p-type) TCMs has proven more difficult due to the deep valence band and high hole effective masses found in many wide band-gap p-type semiconductors.^{2,5,6} As a consequence, the FOM of the current state-of-the-art p-type TCMs is more than two orders of magnitude lower than in the best n-type oxides.^{7,8} If this limitation were overcome, the design options for optoelectronic devices would be greatly expanded and fully transparent electronics could be realized.^{2,5,6}

A promising p-type TCM is the binary compound CuI. Although its transparency and conductivity have been known for over a century,⁹ it was only recently discovered that growing CuI by reactive sputtering could enhance its FOM up to the highest values observed for any p-type TCMs.⁷ Since these results were achieved without any (intentional) extrinsic doping, CuI has significant potential for further improvement by the controlled incorporation of acceptor impurities such as the Group VI elements O, S, and Se.¹⁰ CuI has several electronic features that can promote a high hole conductivity by native doping: an antibonding valence band with strong dispersion due to Cu d-I p hybridization,¹¹ a low formation energy for Cu vacancies,¹² the lack of compensating native dopants,¹³ and the clustering of Cu vacancies

into ordered structures that stabilize a Cu-deficient stoichiometry.¹²

Interestingly, many halide compounds such as SnI_2 , PbI_2 , and hybrid halide perovskites ($\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ and similar) undergo major bulk reactions and structural changes when exposed to moisture.¹⁶ On the other hand, CuI is structurally stable under ambient conditions and is relatively hydrophobic based on contact angle measurements,¹⁷⁻¹⁹ although perovskite solar cells employing CuI as a hole transport layer still exhibit instability at the device level.²⁰ Even though the bulk structure of CuI is unaffected by exposure to ambient air and humidity, properties of crucial importance for TCM applications (e.g., electrical conductivity and work function) can be sensitive to much smaller amounts of adsorbed water or oxygen than the quantities necessary for bulk reactions. Previous work on stability of the electrical conductivity in CuI focused only on long time scales (weeks or months).^{7,21} In a similar fashion, the CuI work function reported in several papers was measured after an undefined exposure time to air, without investigating the effect of oxygen or moisture on the work function of a pristine CuI surface.^{18,22-27} In this work, we investigate changes in the conductivity, work function, and ionization energy of CuI in the first few hours of exposure to air at different relative humidities (RH).

Experimental details

250 nm-thick CuI films were grown on fused silica glass by gas-phase iodization of sputter-deposited metallic Cu films, similar to previous reports.^{9,28} Iodization was performed by placing the Cu films on a hotplate next to iodine pellets, covering both the films and a pellet with an upside-down Petri dish, heating the hotplate to 100°C over 2 min, and removing the iodized films from the hotplate 5 min after reaching the temperature setpoint. The films were immediately placed into a nitrogen-filled transport box before characterizing either the electrical conductivity or the surface electronic properties. The time between growth interruption and the first measurement point was 5 min for conductivity measure-

ments and 10 min for surface measurements. Conductivity measurements were performed with a collinear four-point probe in a humidity-controlled chamber under normal indoor lighting. Work function and ionization energy measurements were performed in the dark using a combined Kelvin probe (KP)/ambient pressure photoemission spectroscopy (PES) system (SKP-5050 and APS-02, KP Technology). Work function and ionization energy were measured sequentially on the same sample as a function of ambient exposure time by using the same tip as a Kelvin probe and as a photoelectron detector.¹⁴ The ionization energy (Fig. 1) can be determined by linear regression and extrapolation of $Y^{\frac{1}{3}}(E)$ spectra or of $Y^{\frac{1}{2}}(E)$ spectra as shown in Fig. 1. $Y(E)$ is the photoelectron yield versus photon energy E , measured by illuminating the sample with monochromated UV light.¹⁴ The $Y^{\frac{1}{3}}$ method is appropriate for nondegenerate semiconductors,¹⁵ whereas the $Y^{\frac{1}{2}}$ method is appropriate for degenerate semiconductors or metals.¹⁴ As will be explained later, the Fermi level of the CuI surface changes as a function of ambient exposure time, so both methods are shown in Fig. 1. Work function measurements were calibrated by first measuring the work function of a gold reference sample by PES using the $Y^{\frac{1}{2}}$ method, and by then measuring the contact potential difference (CPD) between the gold reference and the KP tip to determine the tip's work function. The work function of the CuI films was then calculated by adding the measured CuI-tip CPD to the work function of the tip.

Results and discussion

Basic structural characterization (Figs. S1,S2, Supporting Information) confirms that the CuI films are in the zincblende phase known for its transparent and conductive properties. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) images show that CuI is polycrystalline with an average grain size of about 500 nm (Fig. S3, Supporting Information). Although the film is largely pinhole-free, it is clear that at least some of the grains are not atomically connected and some voids are present, as often observed in CuI films grown by gas-phase iodization.²¹

Figure 1: Determination of the CuI ionization energy by ambient pressure photoemission spectroscopy 5 min after CuI film growth (a), 65 min after CuI film growth (b), and 48 h after CuI film growth (c). Under the assumption of a nondegenerate (degenerate) semiconductor, the ionization energy can be extracted by linear regression and extrapolation of the $Y^{\frac{1}{3}}$ spectrum ($Y^{\frac{1}{2}}$ spectrum), where Y is the photoelectron yield.^{14,15} The extrapolated values (in eV) are shown. Spectra are normalized.

In fact, the morphology of CuI is similar to our previously reported nanoporous ZnO:Al films deposited by RF sputtering at high pressures (Fig. S3, Supporting Information), which exhibited detectable changes in their electrical properties under exposure to ambient air.⁴ Sub-band gap optical transmission is in the 50-80% range (Fig. S4, Supporting Information). Relatively low sub-band gap transmission is typical for gas-phase-iodized CuI films due to their large surface roughness and consequent optical scattering.²⁹ The conductivity of the present CuI films is lower than in state-of-the-art reactively sputtered CuI⁷ but it is generally compatible with the conductivity of gas-phase-iodized CuI films without extrinsic doping.^{9,21,29} The time evolution of the conductivity for two nominally identical CuI samples is compared in Fig. 2(a). One sample was kept at 35% RH in the humidity chamber, the other sample was kept in a nitrogen-filled glove box with oxygen and water content below 1 ppm. The conductivity of the sample stored in an inert atmosphere slightly decreases over two days. Conversely, the sample stored at ambient humidity experiences a conductivity increase by nearly a factor of two over the first 5 hours after growth. The swift conductivity enhancement is followed by some degradation on a much longer time scale. We verified that the time evolution of the conductivity only depends weakly on the type of background atmosphere (air or nitrogen) but depends strongly on the presence or absence of moisture.

Figure 2: (a): Conductivity as a function of time for a CuI film stored in air at 35% RH, and for a nominally identical film stored in a glove box with water content below 1 ppm. (b): Work function (as measured by KP) and ionization energy (as measured by PES) of a CuI film held at $(35\pm 5)\%$ RH. The shaded region is a guide to the eye. For reasons explained in the main text, the two initial ionization energy data points are determined using the $Y^{\frac{1}{2}}$ method in Fig. 1(a,b), whereas the final data point is determined using the $Y^{\frac{1}{3}}$ method in Fig. 1(c). Error bars are ± 30 meV for both the ionization energy and the work function. (c): Compilation of work function values measured in previous studies. Star markers are used for KP measurements.²²⁻²⁴ Triangle markers are used for UV photoemission spectroscopy (UPS) measurements.^{18,25-27}

Another nominally identical sample was employed for work function and ionization energy measurements in air with laboratory humidity in the $(35\pm 5)\%$ RH range. Similarly to the case of the conductivity, work function and ionization energy undergo rapid changes in the first few hours after growth (Fig. 2(b)). After two days of exposure to ambient humidity, the work function has decreased from 5.70 eV to 4.80 eV and the ionization energy has decreased from 5.57 eV to 4.88 eV using the $Y^{\frac{1}{3}}$ method, or from 5.72 eV to 5.16 eV if the $Y^{\frac{1}{2}}$

Figure 3: (a) Simplified sketch of the mechanism generating a surface dipole by water adsorption on CuI. The average perpendicular component of the dipole moment of a water molecule (μ_{\perp}) is given by the vector average of the individual water dipoles $\bar{\mu}_i$. The surface is drawn as Cu-terminated due to the high volatility of I. (b) Band diagram of a CuI surface shortly after growth ($t = 0$, left side) and after exposure to ambient humidity for 48 hours ($t = 48$ h, right side). VBM and CBM are the valence band maximum and conduction band minimum respectively, and E_{vac} is the vacuum level. Ionization energy and work function data are taken from Fig. 2(b). The band gap E_g is estimated as 3.01 eV using a Tauc plot for direct gap materials (Fig. S5, Supporting Information). Based on this band gap value, the electron affinity of the as-grown surface (2.71 eV) is derived. The surface CBM at $t = 48$ h is drawn assuming no chemical changes at the surface.

method is used (Fig. 1). Work function values reported in the literature^{18,22–27} are plotted in Fig. 2(c). Comparison to our data suggests that the large spread in the previously measured values may be due to different air exposure times and humidity levels in the previous studies. Consistent with this hypothesis, we note that the reported work functions measured by UV photoemission spectroscopy in ultra-high vacuum are generally higher than those measured by Kelvin probe (Fig. 2(c)), which could be due to (partial) water desorption in a vacuum environment. The work function change $\Delta\Phi$ is caused by preferential alignment of the dipole moments of adsorbed water molecules, which generates a net surface dipole. Modeling the water dipole layer as a plane capacitor yields

$$\frac{\Delta\Phi}{e} = \frac{n\mu_{\perp}d}{\epsilon_0\epsilon_r} \quad (1)$$

In Eq. 1, $n \simeq 9.2 \text{ nm}^{-2}$ is the area density of one monolayer (ML) of adsorbed water

molecules, assuming the equilibrium intermolecular separation of 3.55 \AA and hexagonal close packing.³⁰ μ_{\perp} is the surface-normal component of the vector average of the dipole moments of all water molecules (Fig. 3(a)). The number d of adsorbed MLs at 35% RH can be predicted using BET theory, an extension of the Langmuir adsorption model for multi-layer adsorption of gases.³¹ Due to the difference in the enthalpy of adsorption between hydrophobic and hydrophilic surfaces, BET theory predicts that the thickness of the adsorbed species at 35% RH should be 0.5 ML for a strongly hydrophobic surface and 1.5 ML for a strongly hydrophilic surface. Since contact angle measurements indicate that the CuI surface is an intermediate case,^{17,18} we assume $d = 1$ ML. ε_0 and ε_r are the permittivities of vacuum and of the water layer respectively. We take $\varepsilon_r = 1$ because the water molecules generate the dipole field themselves, instead of responding to it as a dielectric. Furthermore, the first ML of adsorbed water is known to be immobile, with $\varepsilon_r \simeq 1$ measured under an externally applied voltage,³² in stark contrast to $\varepsilon_r \simeq 80$ in bulk water. Taking $\Delta\Phi = -0.90 \text{ eV}$ as determined by KP after two days of ambient exposure, we find that $\mu_{\perp} = 0.14 \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, where $\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ is the magnitude of the dipole moment of a single water molecule (1.85 D). Assuming that a close-packed monolayer of adsorbed water has formed on CuI, the surface dipole has therefore around 14% of the maximum dipole strength of a perfectly aligned water monolayer. Since the work function decreases upon water adsorption, $\vec{\mu}_{\perp}$ points away from the CuI film. Therefore adsorbed water is preferentially bonded to the CuI surface through its oxygen atoms (Fig. 3(a)), as systematically observed in many oxides, chalcogenides, and pnictides.^{33,34}

Two features of the plot in Fig. 2(b) require further discussion. The first is the negative shift in the measured work function just before and just after performing a PES measurement. The shift is negligible on the as-grown surface but it becomes larger for increasing ambient exposure time. A substantial shift of -200 meV is observed 48 hours after growth, as shown in detail in Fig. S6(c), Supporting Information. This effect can be explained by photoinduced hydrophilicity, a well-known phenomenon in, e.g., various metal oxides and graphene.^{35,36}

Briefly, the UV radiation used during PES measurements can promote surface hydroxylation by dissociating adsorbed water molecules³⁶ or cause surface structural changes that enhance water adsorption.³⁵ These effects can increase n , d , or μ_{\perp} in Eq. 1, and thus shift the work function to even lower values. However, photoinduced work function changes are at least partially reversible, since the work function slowly increases again with time once UV irradiation is turned off (Fig. S6(c), Supporting Information).

A second issue is the applicability of the $Y^{\frac{1}{3}}$ method versus the $Y^{\frac{1}{2}}$ method to determine the ionization energy of CuI. In the initial stages of water adsorption, the $Y^{\frac{1}{3}}$ method yields an ionization energy that is 130 meV smaller than the work function, implying very high degenerate p-type doping at the surface of the as-grown film. As the $Y^{\frac{1}{3}}$ method is only valid for nondegenerate semiconductors, we conclude that the $Y^{\frac{1}{2}}$ method for degenerate semiconductors is the most appropriate in the initial stages of ambient exposure. In fact, the $Y^{\frac{1}{2}}$ method yields an ionization energy of 5.72 eV on the as-grown surface, which is 20 meV larger than the work function and implies a surface hole density of $1.3 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ according to Fermi-Dirac statistics. This value is fairly close to the bulk hole density obtained directly by Hall effect measurements ($(5.0 \pm 0.5) \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) and indirectly by thermovoltage measurements ($(2 \pm 1) \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$). The assumptions used to derive the hole density from a thermovoltage measurement are discussed in the Supporting Information. A surface band diagram based on these values is sketched on the left side of Fig. 3(b), and labeled as $t = 0$ to represent the as-grown surface. Since the Fermi levels on the as-grown surface and in the bulk are close to each other due to their similar hole concentrations, the CuI bands and the vacuum level are drawn flat. On the other hand, applying the $Y^{\frac{1}{2}}$ method after 48 h of ambient exposure yields an ionization energy that is 360 meV larger than the work function (compare Fig. 1(c) and Fig. 2(b)) significantly outside the applicability range of the method. Hence, the $Y^{\frac{1}{3}}$ method for nondegenerate semiconductors should be employed at this later stage. The corresponding ionization energy is 4.88 eV, which is 80 meV lower than the work function, thus confirming the applicability of the $Y^{\frac{1}{3}}$ method at this stage. A surface band

Figure 4: (a): Conductivity enhancement factor (maximum conductivity divided by initial conductivity) as a function of relative humidity. Each data point refers to a unique CuI film only exposed to a single humidity. The shaded region is a guide to the eye. (b): Conductivity trace of a single CuI sample sequentially exposed to different humidities.

diagram for the ambient-exposed CuI surface is shown on the right side of Fig. 3(b) and is labeled as " $t = 24$ h". The surface dipole, given by $\Delta\Phi = -0.90$ eV, is represented by the abrupt shift in the vacuum level E_{vac} . Since the ionization energy decreases slightly less than the work function from $t = 0$ to $t = 24$ h (-0.84 eV versus -0.90 eV), we do not exclude the possibility of a small VBM downshift at the ambient-exposed surface due to chemical effects (e.g. surface oxidation) or electrostatic effects (e.g. positively charged surface defects).

To investigate the origin of the conductivity enhancement upon water adsorption, the time-dependent conductivity experiment shown in Fig. 2(a) was repeated at six different RHs between 0 and 80%, with a fresh sample grown before each new experiment. At each RH, we plot the ratio between the maximum conductivity over time and the initial conductivity of the as-grown surface (Fig. 4(a)). This conductivity enhancement factor is maximized when RH is around 30-40% and is negligible at very low and very high humidities. Additional CuI samples with a different thickness confirm this trend (Fig. S7, Supporting Information). Simply plotting the maximum conductivity over time versus RH also results in a similar trend (Fig. S8, Supporting Information). Since a RH of 30-40% corresponds to about 1 ML coverage as explained above, we conclude that the conductivity-enhancing mechanism is maximized by the presence of no more than 1 ML of water adsorbed dissociatively or as a molecule at the film surface and at internal surfaces (nanopores and grain boundaries). Furthermore, the time evolution of conductivity and work function are similar to each other

(Figs. 2(a,b)) with a fast initial transient in the first couple of hours after exposure to moist air. Although this correlation may be just a coincidence, the combination of the two above findings provides strong evidence against bulk effects, such as increased hole doping in CuI by incorporation of, e.g., O_I acceptors in the bulk. Instead, the conductivity enhancement may be related to the same effects responsible for the decrease in work function at CuI surfaces, although it cannot simply be attributed to a decrease in contact resistance as the four-point measurement configuration excludes contributions from contact resistance. Another option is the existence of a parallel conduction path through the adsorbed water layer at the film surface, which could lead to an increase in the measured conductivity. However, the conductivity of adsorbed water is not higher than a few mS/cm even under extreme humidity.³⁷ As the conductivity of our as-grown CuI is about three orders of magnitude higher (Fig. 2(a)), the adsorbed water layer cannot be regarded as a high-conductivity path. Surface doping effects can also be excluded because the Fermi level of the humidity-exposed surface (right side of Fig. 3(b)) is further away from the VBM compared to the Fermi level of the as-grown surface (left side of Fig. 3(b)), indicating a lower surface hole concentration after water adsorption.

Instead, we propose an alternative hypothesis for the moisture-enhanced conductivity. The as-grown film surface, nanopore surfaces, and grain boundaries are preferentially iodine-terminated due to the high iodine vapor pressure during growth (about 1 bar). Therefore, water is preferentially adsorbed onto surface iodine atoms immediately after growth and prior to our conductivity and work function measurements. When the films are kept in an iodine-free atmosphere (air or nitrogen) iodine atoms tend to re-evaporate from CuI surfaces due to the high vapor pressure of I. Iodine re-evaporation can be verified by storing CuI films next to a Cu block in a closed box and observing strong coloration of the Cu block after a day of storage. This loss of iodine is likely to alter the nature of CuI surfaces and grain boundaries from I-terminated to Cu-terminated. Together with loss of iodine, the grain boundaries are likely to become hydrated as in various other polycrystalline iodides,

Figure 5: Sum Σ_μ of electron- and hole mobility in a CuI film deposited on fused silica glass, as measured by THz transmission spectroscopy using a 400 nm laser pump to generate free carriers. The dashed lines are fits to the real and imaginary parts of Σ_μ using the Drude model with a carrier effective mass of $0.3 m_e$ and a carrier scattering time of 20 fs. The extrapolated value of Σ_μ at zero frequency (DC electric field) is $120 \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}$.

which are known to experience fast hydration in a humid environment.^{16,38} For example, grain boundaries of hybrid iodide perovskite films can be fully hydrated after a few minutes' exposure to ambient humidity.¹⁶ Therefore we assume that the film surface, pore surfaces, and grain boundaries of CuI become hydrated in a similar time frame as the change in surface- and grain boundary termination.

Based on the above discussion, we hypothesize that the decrease in work function and the increase in conductivity are both related to a time-dependent change in the preferential termination of the film surface and grain boundaries from I-terminated to Cu-terminated. For the case of the film surface, this change in termination is expected to lower the work function of CuI because adsorption of water on the oxygen side is favored on a cation-terminated surface with respect to an anion-terminated surface, thus increasing the strength of a surface dipole pointing away from the film surface (Fig. 3(a)). For the case of grain boundaries, the lattice sites that become available after iodine re-evaporation are likely to be hydrogenated or hydroxylated upon air exposure. Finally, for the case of voids and nanopores, water molecules

may partially fill up the pores and connect some initially disconnected grain surfaces. The effect of hydrogenation and water adsorption on electrical conductivity was studied in detail for silicon nanocrystal films.³⁹ It was found that hydrogenation of the nanocrystals' surfaces and the subsequent water adsorption both contributed to an increase in electrical conductivity. We propose that similar effects may contribute to the enhanced conductivity in CuI films. Grain boundaries may be effectively passivated by hydrogenation or hydroxylation, and water filling of nanopores may open up more physical transport channels across initially disconnected grain surfaces.

If this interpretation of humidity-enhanced conductivity is correct, then grain boundaries and nanopores act as bottlenecks for hole transport in our CuI films. Thus, one would expect the intra-grain hole mobility in CuI to be significantly larger than the long-range hole mobility including transport across various grain boundaries. The former can be measured by THz spectroscopy⁴⁰ and the latter can be measured using the Hall effect. Indeed, our THz spectroscopy measurements on CuI indicate Drude-like conductivity and a value of $120 \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}$ as the sum of carrier mobilities (Fig. 5). On the other hand, our Hall measurements yield a hole mobility of only $(5.4 \pm 0.8) \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}$, in line with previous reports.⁴¹ The electron- and hole effective masses are both around $0.3 m_e$ in CuI,²⁹ where m_e is the electron rest mass. Thus, the mobilities for the two carrier types are not expected to differ by a substantial amount. In fact, the scattering times of electrons and holes would need to differ by a factor of 20 to reconcile the THz and Hall hole mobilities, which is unlikely since p-type doping is not extremely high. Instead, the significant discrepancy between the two measurements is likely due to the limiting effect of grain boundaries on hole mobility, which can be mitigated by grain boundary hydration. Interestingly, previous magnetoresistance experiments attributed the high mobilities of CuI films to tunneling effects across grain boundaries, although the effect of grain boundary hydration was not considered.⁴² There are no reasons to expect that passivation of CuI grain boundaries should improve past the humidity level at which the grain boundaries are fully hydrated. In fact, the conductivity enhancement factor drops

at humidities higher than 30-40% RH (Fig. 4(a)) due to other unidentified loss mechanisms, such as water absorption in the bulk, or to a too large surface dipole.

Finally, we show in Fig. 4(b) that humidity-dependent conductivity changes have both a reversible and an irreversible component. Unlike the case of Fig. 4(a), in this experiment the *same* sample was exposed to different humidities sequentially, and its conductivity was monitored. At each RH change, the measured conductivity changes consistently with the data in Fig. 4(a). For example, the conductivity increases when moving from 17% to 60% RH or from 60% to 35% RH, and it decreases when moving from 35% to 20% RH or from 20% to 10% RH (Fig. 4(b)). However, there is also a long-term overall trend of decreasing conductivity, as evident when comparing the conductivity at 35% RH after ~ 50 hr and the conductivity at 30% and 40% RH after ~ 120 hr. Slow iodine re-evaporation from the bulk of the film could be responsible for this effect, since we also observe a slow decrease in conductivity in a CuI film stored in a water-free atmosphere in nitrogen (Fig. 2(a)).

Conclusion

CuI films exposed to moist air experience a conductivity increase and a work function decrease over a similar time frame (a couple of hours). We hypothesize that the conductivity increase is due to passivation of grain boundaries and filling of nanopores by water in molecular or dissociated form, thus enhancing the hole mobility across grain boundaries. The conductivity increase is partially reversible and is maximized at 30-40% RH, which probably corresponds to one monolayer of adsorbed water at the film surface. We encourage other researchers to report the atmosphere exposure time and humidity level when presenting CuI characterization results.

Supplementary information

See supplementary material for structural characterization by XRD and Raman spectroscopy, band gap determination by optical spectroscopy, additional humidity-dependent conductivity experiments, and more detailed plots of the initial and final phases of the conductivity, work function, and ionization energy measurements.

Acknowledgements

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 840751. We acknowledge Lars Steinkopf, Sergiu Levcenko, José Márquez Prieto, Pascal Becker, and Ole Hansen for technical assistance and helpful discussions.

References

- (1) Ellmer, K. Past achievements and future challenges in the development of optically transparent electrodes. *Nature Photonics* **2012**, *6*, 809–817.
- (2) Morales-Masis, M.; De Wolf, S.; Woods-Robinson, R.; Ager, J. W.; Ballif, C. Transparent Electrodes for Efficient Optoelectronics. *Advanced Electronic Materials* **2017**, *3*, 1600529.
- (3) Gordon, R. G. Criteria for Choosing Transparent Conductors. *MRS Bulletin* **2000**, *25*, 52–57.
- (4) Crovetto, A.; Ottsen, T. S.; Stamate, E.; Kjær, D.; Schou, J.; Hansen, O. On performance limitations and property correlations of Al-doped ZnO deposited by radio-frequency sputtering. *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics* **2016**, *49*, 295101.

- (5) Fioretti, A. N.; Morales-Masis, M. Bridging the p-type transparent conductive materials gap: synthesis approaches for disperse valence band materials. *Journal of Photonics for Energy* **2020**, *10*, 042002.
- (6) Kawazoe, H.; Yasukawa, M.; Hyodo, H.; Kurita, M.; Yanagi, H.; Hosono, H. P-type electrical conduction in transparent thin films of CuAlO₂. *Nature* **1997**, *389*, 939–942.
- (7) Yang, C.; Kneiß, M.; Lorenz, M.; Grundmann, M. Room-temperature synthesized copper iodide thin film as degenerate p-type transparent conductor with a boosted figure of merit. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **2016**, *113*, 12929–12933.
- (8) Woods-Robinson, R.; Broberg, D.; Faghaninia, A.; Jain, A.; Dwaraknath, S. S.; Persson, K. A. Assessing High-Throughput Descriptors for Prediction of Transparent Conductors. *Chemistry of Materials* **2018**, *30*, 8375–8389.
- (9) Bädeker, K. Über die elektrische Leitfähigkeit und die thermoelektrische Kraft einiger Schwermetallverbindungen. *Annalen der Physik* **1907**, *327*, 749–766.
- (10) Grauzinytė, M.; Botti, S.; Marques, M. A. L.; Goedecker, S.; Flores-Livas, J. A. Computational acceleration of prospective dopant discovery in cuprous iodide. *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics* **2019**, *21*, 18839–18849.
- (11) Li, Y.; Sun, J.; Singh, D. J. Optical and electronic properties of doped p-type CuI: Explanation of transparent conductivity from first principles. *Physical Review Materials* **2018**, *2*, 035003.
- (12) Jaschik, S.; Marques, M. R. G.; Seifert, M.; Rödl, C.; Botti, S.; Marques, M. A. L. Stable Ordered Phases of Cuprous Iodide with Complexes of Copper Vacancies. *Chemistry of Materials* **2019**, *31*, 7877–7882.
- (13) Wang, J.; Li, J.; Li, S.-S. Native p-type transparent conductive CuI via intrinsic defects. *Journal of Applied Physics* **2011**, *110*, 054907.

- (14) Baikie, I. D.; Grain, A. C.; Sutherland, J.; Law, J. Ambient pressure photoemission spectroscopy of metal surfaces. *Applied Surface Science* **2014**, *323*, 45–53.
- (15) Harwell, J. R.; Baikie, T. K.; Baikie, I. D.; Payne, J. L.; Ni, C.; Irvine, J. T. S.; Turnbull, G. A.; Samuel, I. D. W. Probing the energy levels of perovskite solar cells via Kelvin probe and UV ambient pressure photoemission spectroscopy. *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics* **2016**, *18*, 19738–19745.
- (16) Leguy, A. M. A.; Hu, Y.; Campoy-Quiles, M.; Alonso, M. I.; Weber, O. J.; Azarhoosh, P.; van Schilfgaarde, M.; Weller, M. T.; Bein, T.; Nelson, J.; Docampo, P.; Barnes, P. R. F. Reversible Hydration of $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ in Films, Single Crystals, and Solar Cells. *Chemistry of Materials* **2015**, *27*, 3397–3407.
- (17) Shao, S.; Liu, J.; Zhang, J.; Zhang, B.; Xie, Z.; Geng, Y.; Wang, L. Interface-Induced Crystalline Ordering and Favorable Morphology for Efficient Annealing-Free Poly(3-hexylthiophene): Fullerene Derivative Solar Cells. *ACS Applied Materials and Interfaces* **2012**, *4*, 5704–5710.
- (18) Sun, W.; Peng, H.; Li, Y.; Yan, W.; Liu, Z.; Bian, Z.; Huang, C. Solution-Processed Copper Iodide as an Inexpensive and Effective Anode Buffer Layer for Polymer Solar Cells. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* **2014**, *118*, 16806–16812.
- (19) Chen, W.-Y.; Deng, L.-L.; Dai, S.-M.; Wang, X.; Tian, C.-B.; Zhan, X.-X.; Xie, S.-Y.; Huang, R.-B.; Zheng, L.-S. Low-cost solution-processed copper iodide as an alternative to PEDOT:PSS hole transport layer for efficient and stable inverted planar heterojunction perovskite solar cells. *Journal of Materials Chemistry A* **2015**, *3*, 19353–19359.
- (20) Sepalage, G. A.; Meyer, S.; Pascoe, A.; Scully, A. D.; Huang, F.; Bach, U.; Cheng, Y.-B.; Spiccia, L. Copper(I) Iodide as Hole-Conductor in Planar Perovskite Solar Cells: Probing the Origin of J - V Hysteresis. *Advanced Functional Materials* **2015**, *25*, 5650–5661 .

- (21) Raj, V.; Lu, T.; Lockrey, M.; Liu, R.; Kremer, F.; Li, L.; Liu, Y.; Tan, H. H.; Jagadish, C. Introduction of TiO₂ in CuI for Its Improved Performance as a p-Type Transparent Conductor. *ACS Applied Materials and Interfaces* **2019**, *11*, 24254–24263.
- (22) Rojas, H. C.; Bellani, S.; Fumagalli, F.; Tullii, G.; Leonardi, S.; Mayer, M. T.; Schreier, M.; Grätzel, M.; Lanzani, G.; Di Fonzo, F.; Antognazza, M. R. Polymer-based photocathodes with a solution-processable cuprous iodide anode layer and a polyethyleneimine protective coating. *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2016**, *9*, 3710–3723.
- (23) Kaushik, D. K.; Selvaraj, M.; Ramu, S.; Subrahmanyam, A. Thermal evaporated Copper Iodide (CuI) thin films: A note on the disorder evaluated through the temperature dependent electrical properties. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells* **2017**, *165*, 52–58.
- (24) Das, S.; Choi, J.-Y.; Alford, T. P3HT:PC61BM based solar cells employing solution processed copper iodide as the hole transport layer. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells* **2015**, *133*, 255–259.
- (25) Yoon, S.; Kim, H.; Shin, E.-Y.; Noh, Y.-Y.; Park, B.; Hwang, I. Thickness dependence of a CuI hole transport layer on initial photostability and photovoltaic performance of organic solar cells. *physica status solidi (a)* **2016**, *213*, 2431–2437.
- (26) Shao, S.; Liu, J.; Zhang, J.; Zhang, B.; Xie, Z.; Geng, Y.; Wang, L. Interface-Induced Crystalline Ordering and Favorable Morphology for Efficient Annealing-Free Poly(3-hexylthiophene): Fullerene Derivative Solar Cells. *ACS Applied Materials and Interfaces* **2012**, *4*, 5704–5710.
- (27) Jeon, K.; Jee, H.; Park, M. J.; Lim, S.; Jeong, C. Characterization of the copper iodide hole-selective contact for silicon solar cell application. *Thin Solid Films* **2018**, *660*, 613–617.

- (28) Crovetto, A.; Hajjifarassar, A.; Hansen, O.; Seger, B.; Chorkendorff, I.; Vesborg, P. C. K. Parallel Evaluation of the BiI₃, BiOI, and Ag₃BiI₆ Layered Photoabsorbers. *Chemistry of Materials* **2020**, *32*, 3385–3395.
- (29) Grundmann, M.; Schein, F.-L.; Lorenz, M.; Böntgen, T.; Lenzner, J.; von Wenckstern, H. Cuprous iodide: A p-type transparent semiconductor, history, and novel applications. *physica status solidi (a)* **2013**, *210*, 1671–1703 .
- (30) Wensink, E. J. W.; Hoffmann, A. C.; Apol, M. E. F.; Berendsen, H. J. C. Properties of Adsorbed Water Layers and the Effect of Adsorbed Layers on Interparticle Forces by Liquid Bridging. *Langmuir* **2000**, *16*, 7392–7400.
- (31) Brunauer, S.; Emmett, P. H.; Teller, E. Adsorption of Gases in Multimolecular Layers. *Journal of the American Chemical Society* **1938**, *60*, 309–319.
- (32) McCafferty, E.; Pravdic, V.; Zettlemoyer, A. C. Dielectric behaviour of adsorbed water films on the α -Fe₂O₃ surface. *Transactions of the Faraday Society* **1970**, *66*, 1720.
- (33) Stevanović, V.; Lany, S.; Ginley, D. S.; Tumas, W.; Zunger, A. Assessing capability of semiconductors to split water using ionization potentials and electron affinities only. *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics* **2014**, *16*, 3706.
- (34) Mayer, T.; Klein, A.; Lang, O.; Pettenkofer, C.; Jaegermann, W. H₂O adsorption on the layered chalcogenide semiconductors WSe₂, InSe and GaSe. *Surface Science* **1992**, *269-270*, 909–914.
- (35) Miyauchi, M.; Nakajima, A.; Watanabe, T.; Hashimoto, K. Photocatalysis and Photoinduced Hydrophilicity of Various Metal Oxide Thin Films. *Chemistry of Materials* **2002**, *14*, 2812–2816.
- (36) Xu, Z.; Ao, Z.; Chu, D.; Younis, A.; Li, C. M.; Li, S. Reversible Hydrophobic to

- Hydrophilic Transition in Graphene via Water Splitting Induced by UV Irradiation. *Scientific Reports* **2015**, *4*, 6450.
- (37) Guckenberger, R.; Heim, M.; Cevc, G.; Knapp, H.; Wiegrabe, W.; Hillebrand, A. Scanning tunneling microscopy of insulators and biological specimens based on lateral conductivity of ultrathin water films. *Science* **1994**, *266*, 1538–1540.
- (38) Bradley Phipps, J.; Johnson, D.; Whitmore, D. Effect of composition and imperfections on ion transport in lithium iodine. *Solid State Ionics* **1981**, *5*, 393–396.
- (39) Rastgar, N.; Rowe, D. J.; Anthony, R. J.; Merritt, B. A.; Kortshagen, U. R.; Aydil, E. S. Effects of Water Adsorption and Surface Oxidation on the Electrical Conductivity of Silicon Nanocrystal Films. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* **2013**, *117*, 4211–4218
- .
- (40) Hempel, H.; Redinger, A.; Repins, I.; Moisan, C.; Larramona, G.; Dennler, G.; Handwerg, M.; Fischer, S. F.; Eichberger, R.; Unold, T. Intragrain charge transport in kesterite thin films—Limits arising from carrier localization. *Journal of Applied Physics* **2016**, *120*, 175302.
- (41) Schein, F.-L.; von Wenckstern, H.; Grundmann, M. Transparent p-CuI/n-ZnO heterojunction diodes. *Applied Physics Letters* **2013**, *102*, 092109.
- (42) Kneiß, M.; Yang, C.; Barzola-Quiquia, J.; Benndorf, G.; von Wenckstern, H.; Esquinazi, P.; Lorenz, M.; Grundmann, M. Suppression of Grain Boundary Scattering in Multifunctional p-Type Transparent γ -CuI Thin Films due to Interface Tunneling Currents. *Advanced Materials Interfaces* **2018**, *5*, 1701411.

Figure 6: Table of content graphic.